

Halogenation. Part VI. Bromination and Iodination of Benzonitrile.

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Bromo and iodo derivatives of benzonitrile have been obtained before by indirect methods only either from the corresponding aniline derivatives by the replacement of amino group by cyanogen or from the corresponding benzoic acid derivatives by the replacement of carboxyl group by cyanogen group. It is reported that the action of bromine on benzonitrile under ordinary conditions results in the formation of benzonitrile monobromide and dibromide, whereas in a sealed tube at 200°-360° it results in the formation of perbromobenzonitrile (Engler, *Annalen*, 1865, 133, 144; 1867, 142, 74; Friedburg, *ibid.*, 1871, 188, 29). Bromine or iodine alone, or in presence of other substances such as nitric or sulphuric acids, does not yield any bromo or iodo derivatives of benzonitrile, but the bromo and iodo derivatives have now been obtained by the action of potassium bromide or potassium iodide and concentrated sulphuric acid on benzonitrile.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Action of potassium bromide and sulphuric acid on benzonitrile.—Strong sulphuric acid (5 c.c.) was taken in a test tube and benzonitrile (10 c.c.) was carefully poured into it over the heavy layer of sulphuric acid, care being taken not to allow the acid to mix freely with benzonitrile. Potassium bromide (4 g.) was then slid down the side of the test tube when bromine was set free by the action of sulphuric acid and reacted with benzonitrile which turned gradually into a solid product. At the end of 3 hours the upper solid layer was removed and treated with a small quantity of cold water, shaken and filtered. On evaporating the filtrate to dryness and recrystallising the solid product from cold water, a white crystalline substance (2.5 g.), melting at 112°, was obtained. It was found to be *p*-bromobenzonitrile. (Found: N, 7.48; Br, 43.66. C_6H_4BrCN requires N, 7.7; Br, 43.97 per cent). The residue was digested with water at

50° and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated and allowed to cool, when needle-shaped crystals (0.6 g.), melting at 52°, were obtained. It was found to be *o*-bromobenzonitrile. (Found: Br, 43.72. C_6H_4BrCN requires Br, 43.97 per cent).

The solid residue still left behind was boiled with water and filtered. The filtrate was evaporated to dryness and crystallised from boiling water. The product (0.8 g.) so obtained, m. p. 121°, was found to be benzoic acid. The last portion of the residue was digested with alcohol and crystallised from it, m. p. 128° and was found to be benzamide (0.4 g.). (Found: N, 11.59. C_7H_7ON requires N, 11.57 per cent).

Action of potassium iodide and sulphuric acid on benzonitrile.—Benzonitrile (10 c. c.) was treated with strong sulphuric acid (5 c.c.) and potassium iodide (4 g.) exactly in the same way as in the preceding experiment. Benzonitrile layer was kept cold by pouring cold water over it under the tap. It solidified, the solid was removed after 3 hours and treated successively with cold water, water at 50°, boiling water and finally with alcohol. Solid crystalline products were obtained from these solvents. *p*-Iodobenzonitrile (2 g.). (Found: N, 6.28. I, 55.12; C_6H_4ICN requires N, 6.1; I, 55.46 per cent). *o*-Iodobenzonitrile (0.7 g.) (Found: I, 54.83. C_6H_4ICN requires I, 55.46 per cent). Benzoic acid (0.7 g.) and benzamide (1.1 g.) were also obtained.

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